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EOSC Federated Search Service and PID Graph Service

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Deliverable Abstract

This report presents the development and production release of two core components of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project: the Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph) and the PID Graph (PIDGraph). RDGraph offers a federated search service enhanced with intelligent tools for exploring research outputs across EOSC and beyond, while PIDGraph aggregates records and links provided by PID authority data sources and other trusted sources to support third-party integration and data consumption through APIs and data files, and provides a Data Usage Statistics.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CC	Citation Count or Creative Commons (depends on the context)
COUNTER	Counting Online Usage of Networked Electronic Resources
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ER	Entity-Relationship (Model/Diagram)
FC4E	FAIRCORE4EOSC
IGSN	International Generic Sample Number
IF	Interoperability Framework
LLM	Large Language Model
MDC	Make Data Count (Initiative)
NL	Natural Language
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PID	Persistent Identifier
PLM	Pre-Trained Language Model
RA	Registration Agency (e.g., DOI Registration Agency)
RAiD	Research Activity Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDGraph	Research Discovery Graph
REST (API)	Representational State Transfer (API)
ROR	Research Organisation Registry
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SKG-IF	Scientific Knowledge Graphs – Interoperability Framework
SQL	Structural Querying Language
TSV	Tab Separated File
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience (Design)
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	General approach	3
3	Implementation	4
3.1	The EOSC Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph) Service.....	4
3.1.1	Component Overview.....	4
3.1.2	Design & development.....	5
3.1.3	Code & resources availability	21
3.2	The EOSC PID Graph Service (PIDGraph)	22
3.2.1	Component Overview.....	22
3.2.2	Design & development.....	23
3.2.3	Code & resources availability	31
4	Demonstrators	32
4.1	Introduction and background.....	32
4.2	The Demonstrator subtasks.....	33
4.2.1	B2FIND Integration into RDGraph.....	33
4.2.2	B2FIND exposure of metadata to Open Knowledge Graphs	34
4.2.3	PIDGraph metadata integration in B2FIND.....	35
5	Engagement, communication, and user community reception.....	37
5.1	RDGraph.....	37
5.2	PIDGraph	37
6	Sustainability.....	38
6.1	RDGraph.....	38
6.2	PIDGraph	38
7	Conclusions	39
	References	40
	Appendix I. Conceptual Mapping from the OpenAIRE Graph to the RDGraph.....	41

List of Figures

Figure 1 - High-level architecture of the RDGraph component.	4
Figure 2 - The SKG-IF data model.	6
Figure 3 - RDGraph ER Data Model.	7
Figure 4 - RDGraph ER Data Model subset.	8
Figure 5 - Recommender Router.	13
Figure 6 - Screenshot of the main search UI of the RDGraph portal.	15
Figure 7 - Screenshot of the advanced search.	15
Figure 8 - A search result showing impact indicators.	16
Figure 9 - The options for ranking search results.	16
Figure 10 - Example of a search using Software Heritage IDs.	16
Figure 11 - Main UI of the NL search.	17
Figure 12 - Results of the NL Search.	17
Figure 13 - Screenshot of the researcher-centric recommender.	18
Figure 14 - Screenshot of the field-specific recommender.	19
Figure 15 - Screenshot of the similarity-based recommender.	19
Figure 16 - Searching for research activities.	20
Figure 17 - An example recommended RAiD.	20
Figure 18 - UI to redirect to RAiD registration.	21
Figure 19- A diagram showing the data flow through the PIDGraph services.	23
Figure 20 - An example query in the GraphQL API, demonstrating the ability to search by PID, and retrieve a selected subset of metadata for the node, as well as metadata from connected nodes.	24
Figure 21 - A search in DataCite Commons filtered to only return results from RAiD Registries.	25
Figure 22 - The DataCite Commons page for a Data Management Plan, showing the visual representations of connections through the graph.	26
Figure 23 - The DataCite Commons page for one of the contributors involved in the Data Management Plan shown in the previous figure.	27
Figure 24 - A graph showing the increase in the vertices contained within the PIDGraph over the lifetime of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.	28
Figure 25 - Views and download counts for DataCite DOIs from CERN.	29
Figure 26 - B2FIND relations to FC4E services.	32
Figure 27 - Ingestion of B2FIND metadata into RDGraph.	34
Figure 28 - PIDGraph citation count information integrated in B2FIND search result.	35
Figure 29 - PIDGraph RAiD connection in B2FIND search result.	36

List of Tables

Table 1 - List of RDGraph-related code repositories.	21
Table 2 - List of PIDGraph-related code repositories.	31

Executive Summary

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the technical developments carried out in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project under Work Package 3 (WP3), focusing on the design, implementation, and production release of two key components: the Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph) and the PID Graph.

The RDGraph is an EOSC Federated Search Service that enables cross-repository and cross-community discovery of research entities—including publications, data, software, and activities—by leveraging graph-based models and natural language processing. It extends the EOSC Catalogue with support for additional entities such as Research Activity Identifiers (RAiDs) and offers multiple access methods including user-friendly interfaces, APIs, and open data dumps to ensure interoperability and reuse.

The PIDGraph aggregates metadata and persistent identifier (PID) relationships from authoritative sources such as ORCID, ROR, Crossref, and DataCite. It is designed to support third-party integration and data consumption through APIs and data files, and provides a Data Usage Statistics Service that aligns with the EOSC's vision of a connected, open research infrastructure.

The development of both components followed an agile and iterative approach, emphasizing early prototyping, modular design, and continuous stakeholder engagement. Regular interactions with use case leaders and demonstrators ensured that the systems evolved in line with real-world needs, enabling timely beta releases and refinements based on user feedback.

Active engagement and outreach efforts played a critical role in the success of both components. Both components were showcased through webinars, conferences, and dedicated workshops with demonstrators, case studies, and end users.

Regarding sustainability, RDGraph will continue to be supported and maintained within the OpenAIRE infrastructure, ensuring long-term integration into EOSC services. PIDGraph will remain openly accessible and actively developed by DataCite, with multiple access options including the DataCite Commons portal, APIs, and downloadable datasets.

Together, RDGraph and PIDGraph represent significant contributions to the European Open Science Cloud, advancing discoverability, interoperability, and reuse of research outputs across disciplines and communities.

1 Introduction

This deliverable is the final report summarising the development activities carried out in WP3 of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project and documenting the production release of the relevant components: the *Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph)* service, which is an EOSC Federated Search Service, and the *PID Graph*.

The EOSC Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph) service is a federated search service across EOSC repositories and communities as well as additional, well-established scholarly data sources (like Crossref) that comes together with a suite of advanced discovery tools. RDGraph extends the content of the OpenAIRE Graph supporting additional entities like the Research Activity Identifiers (RAiDs), while offering functionality similar to several community-oriented discovery tools. The discovery tools of the RDGraph service exploit natural language processing and graph-based solutions for EOSC users to explore research-related entities (e.g., publications, data, software, activities). The RDGraph is accessible via intuitive UI/UX portals, open data dumps, and open APIs to support data re-use, third-party service interoperability, and even the creation of value-added services.

The EOSC PID Graph Service (PIDGraph) is a component designed to provide services for the continuous population of and access provision to a PID Graph, which consists in the aggregation of records and links provided by PID authority data sources, such as ORCID, ROR, DataCite, and Crossref, and other trusted services. The PIDGraph is available via regular data dumps comprising metadata for DOIs and links between PIDs in the graph, as well as via APIs supporting third party integration via common protocols (e.g. GraphQL, OAI-PMH, OpenAPI REST), and the provisioning of a Data Usage Statistics Service allowing integration of COUNTER-compliant statistics into the graph.

The following sections are structured as follows: Section 2 presents an overview of the approach taken for the development of the two components. Section 3 delves into the implementation details for each component and describes related activities. Section 4 briefly discusses how the components were used in the context of the FAIRCORE4EOSC demonstration activities. Section 5 highlights engagement and outreach efforts, while Section 6 offers initial insights into the sustainability prospects of RDGraph and PIDGraph. Finally, Section 7 concludes the report by summarising the key takeaways.

2 General approach

The development of RDGraph and PIDGraph followed an agile, iterative approach centered on early prototyping and continuous refinement. From the outset, the focus was on ensuring that both components evolved in close alignment with the project's overarching goals and the real-world needs of end. To achieve this, the technical teams maintained active and regular communication with project stakeholders, including use case leaders and demonstrator partners. This collaboration enabled early validation of concepts and facilitated a shared understanding of system requirements. Frequent meetings and progress reviews created an environment of transparency and adaptability, allowing the teams to respond quickly to challenges and feedback as development progressed.

In both cases, sub-components were initially developed independently, allowing for parallel development and technical flexibility. This modular approach enabled the teams to advance at different paces, depending on the specific needs and maturity of each solution. Beta versions of RDGraph and PIDGraph were released on time for the FAIRCORE4EOSC beta release, serving as functional prototypes to collect feedback from relevant partners and users. This feedback was instrumental in refining functionality and improving usability. Once matured, the subcomponents were integrated into cohesive systems, with development efforts converging toward stable, unified platforms that reflect both technical robustness and user-driven design.

3 Implementation

The next sections outline the design and implementation of the RDGraph (Section 3.1) and the PIDGraph (Section 3.2) services.

3.1 The EOSC Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph) Service

3.1.1 Component Overview

The EOSC Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph) is fundamentally linked to the OpenAIRE Graph, as the former is built upon the OpenAIRE Graph processing pipeline. This pipeline encompasses the harvesting, construction, enrichment, and provisioning of graph data. Specifically, the RDGraph's generation involves workflows that are scheduled to operate on the content of the EOSC resource catalogue, which is itself powered by the OpenAIRE Graph. Therefore, the OpenAIRE Graph serves as a core source of data for the RDGraph, providing the foundation for its structure and content.

On top of the Graph, a suite of intelligent discovery tools designed to enhance the exploration of research outputs and services within the EOSC ecosystem are offered. These include natural language search, which leverages techniques to convert user questions into structured queries, enabling intuitive and accessible search experiences. The impact-based search functionality utilizes citation networks and graph analysis to uncover high-impact resources. Additionally, community recommendation profiles are built by mining user activity to capture preferences, frequently accessed results, and behavioral patterns, enabling personalized recommendations through advanced sequence- and graph-based algorithms. Finally, RDGraph supports the inference of RAiDs (Research Activity Identifiers) by applying pattern mining and machine learning to detect potential RAiDs within the RDGraph network, further enriching the research discovery landscape.

Finally, RDGraph data are also accessible through regular data dumps and robust APIs, ensuring seamless interoperability with third-party services, being aligned with well-established standards in the EOSC's interoperability framework.

Figure 1 offers a diagram illustrating the high-level architecture of the RDGraph component.

Figure 1 - High-level architecture of the RDGraph component.

3.1.2 Design & development

3.1.2.1 RDGraph Core

In the next paragraphs, we elaborate on the technical details related to various activities related to the implementation of the RDGraph core.

3.1.2.1.1 RAiD extension

The RDGraph data model extension enabling the integration of RAiD records was facilitated by the inherent flexibility of the OpenAIRE Graph in representing research products and their interconnections. Based on this approach accommodating new types of entities and relationships beyond the initial scope of publications, datasets, and software was relatively easy.

The concept of RAiDs aligns well with the OpenAIRE Graph's capacity to represent research products and the relationships between them. RAiDs were intended to function as research products themselves, representing a specific scientific endeavor. Their primary purpose is to group together various research outputs (publications, datasets, software), research activities (projects), and the organizations involved.

Therefore, extending the RDGraph to include RAiDs likely involved:

- ④ Defining RAiDs as a new type of research product or a distinct entity within the RDGraph model. This could leverage the Research products, Persons, and Organisations entity types.
- ④ Establishing new types of relationships to connect RAiDs with the existing entities in the graph. For instance, relationships could be created to link a RAiD to the research products it encompasses, the grant/project it represents, and the involved organizations and researchers. The OpenAIRE Graph's ability to represent and enrich relations would be crucial here.
- ④ Utilizing the work done in WP4 on the EOSC Research Activity Identifier Service (RAiD). The development of the RAiD service itself provided the conceptual model and potentially the metadata schema for RAiDs, which could then be mapped into the RDGraph. However, the maturity of the contents in the RAiD registry published in Datacite did not allow a full revision of the mapping towards OpenAIRE within the project end. This work will continue after the end of the project.
- ④ Employing inference mechanisms. As mentioned in Section 3.1.2.1.2, an algorithms for "Inference of RAiDs via RDGraph analysis was designed, implemented, and integrated into the RDGraph pipeline.

In conclusion, the extension of the RDGraph data model to accommodate RAiDs was likely possible due to the inherent flexibility of the underlying OpenAIRE Graph architecture in representing diverse research entities and their relationships. By defining RAiDs conceptually within the existing framework as a new type of research product or a central aggregator, and by establishing new relationships to link them with relevant entities like publications, datasets, organizations, and projects (potentially represented through grants), the RDGraph could effectively represent and leverage RAiDs for enhanced research discovery and contextualization.

3.1.2.1.2 The RDGraph data model & relational representation

The RDGraph data model was developed to facilitate advanced discovery tools across EOSC resources and communities and it reuses content from the EOSC catalogue. The definition of the RDGraph data model is derived from the EOSC Resource Catalogue Data Model to address the discovery and statistics needed for the project's activities. The RDGraph model is also being mapped towards the RDA's SKG-IF (Scholarly Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework) data model. Figure 2 presents an overview of the version of the SKG-IF data model used during the RDGraph activities.

Figure 2 - The SKG-IF data model.

An important task to implement the RDGraph core was to map OpenAIRE Graph concepts to SKG-IF ones, creating the RDGraph model. The conceptual mapping from the OpenAIRE Graph to the RDGraph is detailed in Appendix I.

To support the Natural Language Search (NL Search) and Community Recommendation Profiles systems, it was necessary to design and implement a relational representation of the existing graph model. The underlying RDGraph architecture—based on the OpenAIRE graph processing pipeline and leveraging batch processing technologies such as Apache Spark and Hive—was not ideally suited for the low-latency, interactive demands of these prototypes. As a result, a relational version of a relevant subset of the RDGraph was developed to enable more efficient data storage and faster retrieval, better aligning with the performance requirements of the prototype systems. Key aspects of this work included:

- ⦿ **Defining a Representative Subset of the RDGraph:** to manage data volume and resource requirements, it was decided that the prototypes would operate on a representative subset of the RDGraph contents rather than the entire graph. As a result, tailored OpenAIRE graph subsets were created for specific communities of interest. These initially included "Digital Humanities and cultural heritage," "DARIAH EU," "Energy Research," "Transport Research," and a time-constrained subset, with a later addition of mathematics data from ZBMATH. A relational database containing data from these academic communities extracted from the OpenAIRE Graph / RDGraph was set up.
- ⦿ **Designing a Common Database Model:** an Entity-Relationship (ER) data model was designed to be used by both the NL Search and Community Recommender systems. This model focused on entities and relationships directly mappable from the RDGraph and deemed relevant for the functionalities of the prototypes. This model is visually represented in Figure 3 and it is further detailed in the M24 report.

- Developing the RDGraph ER Data Model Subset: Building upon the common database model, a specific RDGraph ER data model subset was defined, it is illustrated below and it is further detailed in the M24 report. This model outlined the specific entities and their attributes that would be extracted and transformed from the RDGraph. The key entities included are presented in Figure 4.
- Implementing Data Extraction and Transformation Workflows: Workflows for the scheduled generation of the RDGraph data in a relational format were implemented. As a first step, a subset of the RDGraph relevant to the prototypes was dumped into a set of tab-separated files (TSV), with one file corresponding to each table in the defined ER model. This involved mapping specific fields from the RDGraph to the attributes of the relational model for each entity. A workflow for applying the mapping from the internal RDGraph model towards the relational representation was also implemented.
- Establishing a PostgreSQL Database: To support low-latency interactions, the extracted data was stored in a dedicated PostgreSQL database.
- Enriching the Relational Representation: the database dump was enriched with additional information. Effort was given on maintaining and updating the mappings between the internal RDGraph model and the relational representation as the RDGraph evolved.
- Facilitating Prototype Development: Providing this relational representation, enabled the developers of the NL Search and Community Recommendation Profiles systems to efficiently query and utilize the RDGraph data for training, testing, and demonstrating their prototypes. For instance, we developed a service using a neural pre-trained language model that translates natural language queries into SQL queries executable on this relational database. Similarly, the recommender system utilized the relational database to access user interactions and research product information.

Figure 3 - RDGraph ER Data Model.

In essence, the work in designing a relational representation of the RDGraph was crucial for enabling the development and demonstration of the interactive prototypes in Task 3.3. By creating a more manageable and

query-friendly data structure from a subset of the large-scale RDGraph, they addressed the specific technical requirements of the NL Search and Community Recommendation Profiles systems. This involved careful data model design, efficient extraction and transformation processes, and the establishment of a suitable database infrastructure. The continuous maintenance and enrichment of this relational representation further supported the iterative development of the prototypes. Notably, the mapping towards the RDA's SKG-IF data model was maintained and updated was ensured, showcasing an effort towards broader interoperability.

Figure 4 - RDGraph ER Data Model subset.

3.1.2.1.3 Generation of the RDGraph

The operations required to support scheduled updates of RDGraph content from the EOSC resource catalogue—including metadata collection, validation, and indexing—were coordinated as part of ongoing development efforts. Support was also provided for the deployment of the software stack necessary to enable the RDGraph data provision workflow. A dedicated process was implemented within this workflow to calculate a set of impact indicators. Additionally, the mapping from the internal RDGraph model was maintained and updated to ensure consistency and alignment with evolving data sources.

3.1.2.1.4 RDGraph APIs

The development and enhancements of REST APIs have been done under the umbrella of the OpenAIRE Graph API. They are documented on the OpenAIRE Graph documentation website.¹

Furthermore, the impact indicators calculated in the RDGraph provision process are used to enable impact-based ranking and filtering of research products via the RDGraph portals and APIs. In addition, special APIs for the integration of the NL Search and recommender services into the RDGraph portals were developed.

¹ <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/apis/graph-api>

3.1.2.1.5 Generation of RDGraph dumps

The complete RDGraph dataset, shared via Zenodo² under the FC4E community, captures structured research data relationships based on the SKG-IF specifications. The current release reflects data as of August 2024 and follows version 1.1 of the SKG-IF specification.³

An updated mapping implementation, aligned with the json-ld based SKG-IF specification,⁴ is scheduled for release by the end of May 2025. This new version will also be made available through the same Zenodo community, ensuring continuity and accessibility for users.

The dataset includes all entities described in the SKG-IF entity specification. Some of these entities (specifically Venues, Topics, and Agents) are generated dynamically during the mapping process. In version 1.1 of the dataset, these "on-the-fly" entities are marked with the prefix tmp. In the json-ld version, the prefix changes to off.

So far, the Agent class only includes persons as agent types. In version 1.1, agent entities are created as they were actual entities in the graph, for authors if they have an ORCID (whether confirmed or pending). In this case, each author is treated as a distinct entity within the graph. The identifiers assigned to them are considered stable; however, due to how the mapping handles ORCID status, the same 16-digit ORCID can result in two different identifiers if it's associated with both a confirmed and a pending ORCID (see the conceptual mapping table above in the document). For all the other person entities in the graph a tmp identifier is provided and the entity is considered local to the specific dataset.

In the version two dataset it's important to note that all the agents marked with the off prefix are not persistent identifiers for the person. These entities are generated in the context of the specific graph and should not be interpreted as globally stable representations of individuals across datasets.

All on-the-fly entities are local to the specific graph they were created for. Their relevance is scoped to that context and may not be reused or referenced across different mappings or datasets.

3.1.2.2 Intelligent Community-oriented Discovery Tools

3.1.2.2.1 Impact-based search

The impact-based search functionality is a subcomponent that is responsible for the calculation of scholarly impact metrics to support scientific discovery and exploration based on citation-based impact. At the core of its creation lies the BIP! Ranker, an open-source, Apache Spark-based implementation designed to efficiently compute a wide range of impact indicators over the contents of the RDGraph. This system leverages scalable distributed processing to handle citation networks involving millions of publications, applying graph mining techniques and iterative algorithms to derive refined, citation-based indicators. The BIP! Ranker is publicly available on GitHub. The respective workflow begins with the ingestion and preprocessing of citation data. Once the respective citation network is constructed, the BIP! Ranker computes multiple bibliometric indicators, such as some variations of PageRank scores. The workflow is fully automated, allowing for regular updates.

The subcomponent calculates citation-based impact indicators for more than 238M distinct PIDs (persistent identifiers) that correspond to research products (scientific publications, datasets, etc). In particular, for each PID, the following indicators (organized in categories based on the semantics of the impact aspect that they better capture) are calculated:

- 🕒 Influence indicators (i.e., indicators of the "total" impact of each research product; how established it is in general)

² <https://zenodo.org/records/13318745>

³ <https://skg-if.readthedocs.io/en/v1.1/model.html>

⁴ <https://skg-if.github.io/>

- Citation Count: The total number of citations of the product, the most well-known influence indicator.
- PageRank score: An influence indicator based on the PageRank, a popular network analysis method. PageRank estimates the influence of each product based on its centrality in the whole citation network. It alleviates some issues of the Citation Count indicator (e.g., two products with the same number of citations can have significantly different PageRank scores if the aggregated influence of the products citing them is very different - the product receiving citations from more influential products will get a larger score).
- 🕒 Popularity indicators (i.e., indicators of the "current" impact of each research product; how popular the product is currently)
 - RAM score: A popularity indicator based on the RAM method. It is essentially a Citation Count where recent citations are considered as more important. This type of "time awareness" alleviates problems of methods like PageRank, which are biased against recently published products (new products need time to receive a number of citations that can be indicative for their impact).
 - AttRank score: A popularity indicator based on the AttRank method. AttRank alleviates PageRank's bias against recently published products by incorporating an attention-based mechanism, akin to a time-restricted version of preferential attachment, to explicitly capture a researcher's preference to examine products which received a lot of attention recently.
- 🕒 Impulse indicators (i.e., indicators of the initial momentum that the research product received right after its publication)
 - Incubation Citation Count (3-year CC): This impulse indicator is a time-restricted version of the Citation Count, where the time window length is fixed for all products and the time window depends on the publication date of the product, i.e., only citations 3 years after each product's publication are counted.

All these scores included inside the RDGraph metadata and are made available via the open RDGraph datasets and API. Additionally, they become available to the RDGraph portal where they can be used for ranking or/and filtering keyword search results.

3.1.2.2.2 Natural Language Search

The Natural Language (NL) Search service allows user to ask questions over the RDGraph without the need for any technical expertise. The service takes care of translating the user's question into a SQL query that can return the requested data, without the need of any user involvement. This way, the user can freely and independently get the data they need, that would otherwise require writing a complex query. This task, also known as Text-to-SQL, has been studied by both the Data Management and Natural Language Processing communities and to this day remains a very challenging problem. As such the development of this service was based on state of the art techniques while also maintaining a low computational cost.

First and foremost, in order to provide a Text-to-SQL solution for the RDGraph we worked closely with OpenAIRE and the rest of our partners to design a relational model of the RDGraph. This model was used to create a relational dump of the graph that can be hosted in a Postgres database where the queries generated by our system are run to return the appropriate results requested by the user. This model was also refined later on in order to support additional queries with attributes that were deemed useful by the project partners.

To build our system, we designed an architecture based on the state-of-the-art approaches in the area: A Large Language Model (LLM) is the core component that receives the user's request along with additional important information and is responsible for generating the appropriate SQL. During the project we experimented with multiple models such as the T5 Pre-Trained Language Model (PLM) and multiple LLMs such as Llama, Qwen, Deepseek, and more. To improve the performance of the LLM we create additional

components that retrieve useful information that is closely related to the user's question. The two main components in question are (1) the few-shot example retriever, and (2) the value linking component.

The few-shot example retriever is responsible for finding Text-to-SQL examples that are similar to the question posed by the user. We implement this component using SentenceBert embeddings and a vector database that allows us to perform efficient similarity search. When the system receives a question, it calculates the embedding of the question and retrieves the most similar examples from a pool of examples that has we hand-crafted for the project (more later on). These examples are then added to the model's input, effectively helping it understand the task it must perform and improving its translation accuracy.

The value linking mechanism is responsible for identifying values stored in the database that are relevant to the user's question and thus essential for generating the correct SQL query. To implement this component, we create a BM25 index that stores textual values from the database and where they are stored (i.e., which table and which column of the DB). When a question is given to the system, this component performs a look up in the index and finds relevant values which are then filtered to reduce noise. The retrieved values are then given to the model's input so that it can choose which ones are useful and incorporate them in the generated query. This is an essential component, especially for a large database such as the RDGraph, because if the model is not aware of how the values are stored it cannot generate correct queries. At the same time the user is not familiar with the inner workings of the database, so we cannot expect them to ask questions using the exact way the values are stored.

As mentioned earlier, we created a dataset of Text-to-SQL examples (i.e., NL Questions and their equivalent SQL Queries) specifically for the purposes of the project and the RDGraph database. Our dataset contains 230 hand-crafted examples that were created by 4 researchers following an iterative process of refinement and corrections to guarantee the quality and correctness of the examples. During the creation process we made sure to cover all the attributes of the database, common questions that were often asked by users, and examples that we identified as pain-points for the system. We use this dataset as a pool for few-shot examples to perform in-context learning (as discussed previously) and to perform fine-tuning, effectively training the model to better understand the database and the requirements of the users.

3.1.2.2.3 Community Recommendation Profiles

The goal of this task is to deliver intelligent services to help users navigate the RDGraph more effectively. As research products (e.g., publications and datasets) grow in volume, identifying relevant results for users becomes increasingly difficult. To this end, we designed and developed three complementary services, each supporting exploration from a different angle:

- 🕒 User-to-Item: recommends publications based on citation behavior within research communities.
- 🕒 Item-to-Item: retrieves similar research products based on content and metadata similarity.
- 🕒 Category-to-Item: guides users exploring research products by category and learns from their interactions in real time.

Each service operates independently but contributes to the common goal of enhancing discovery within research communities.

User-to-Item Recommender

The design and development of the user-to-item recommender focused on adapting an existing collaborative filtering algorithm with state-of-the-art performance [R1] to the specific context of the RDGraph and structuring it around research communities. The first step involved defining the user-item interaction matrix using citation behavior, where users are authors, items are cited publications, and interactions correspond to the frequency of citations. We then prepared and cleaned citation data extracted from the RDGraph, taking care to associate each author and publication with the appropriate research community. In particular, we filtered out authors

whose entire citation activity consisted only of solo-cited results, i.e., publications cited solely by themselves. These interactions offer no collaborative signal for the recommender and were excluded to improve model quality.

Next, we trained separate model instances per community to ensure recommendations were context-aware and tailored to each domain. Initially, the system supported three communities (Darjah EU, Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage, and EOSC) and was later expanded to five with the addition of Energy Research and Transport Research. To deal with the algorithm's quadratic memory complexity ($O(n^2)$), we imposed a cap on the number of candidate publications, selecting the top 100,000 most cited items per community. This trade-off allowed us to balance coverage with performance and resource usage.

To address scalability and runtime performance, we transitioned from an in-memory, on-demand recommendation setup to an offline approach, where recommendations are precomputed and stored in a relational database. This shift drastically reduced memory requirements and enabled fast response times when serving recommendations to users. For cold-start authors (i.e., those with little or no citation activity), we introduced a fallback mechanism that recommends the most cited publications in the author's community.

The development also included the creation of scripts and utilities to support end-to-end operations, including database schema initialization, data ingestion (authors, publications, interactions), model training per community, and exporting recommendation outputs. These tools ensure consistent deployment and ease of updates as new data becomes available. The recommender was integrated with the RDGraph infrastructure, and a demo user interface was added to the portal, allowing users to explore recommendations.

Item-to-Item Recommender

The Item-to-Item Recommender offers content-based suggestions for research products similar to the one a user is currently viewing, helping them quickly find related items that may better suit their needs. The main challenge is defining a similarity measure that is both accurate and scalable to millions of research products in RDGraph.

First, we defined a baseline recommender that calculated pairwise similarities between research products by comparing metadata (type of research product) and text attributes (title, description). To facilitate comparisons, metadata are represented by one-hot encodings, and texts by bag-of-words weighted methods (tf-idf). Then, an aggregation between the metadata and text similarities occurs. This initial version of the recommender was able to provide recommendations on a small subset of the RDGraph (~100K research products). Continuing, two parts required improvement (a) the scalability of the recommender (b) the performance of the recommender, which was constrained by the bag-of-words limitation, not taking into account semantic similarities between texts. To address scalability, we transformed all encodings into vectors and stored them in a FAISS index. The FAISS index enabled low-latency comparisons between vectors managing to scale to 10M research products. To increase recommendation quality, the main focus was to improve comparisons between texts, an important source of information for a research product in the RDGraph. Initial experimentations with LLM embeddings showed weakness in managing to capture the semantics of texts due to their length, mostly focusing on the first phrases only. To address that, we used hierarchical inference based on pairwise similarities [R2] where instead of comparing the full text, the model compares sentences with each other, finding the optimal alignment between the two texts and calculating the similarity. However, such a technique requires pre-computing the similarities, which is computationally too expensive for the size of the RDGraph. Instead, to balance quality and performance, a hybrid approach is used: the Gold recommender, which relies on the computationally intensive but high-quality method, and the Silver recommender, which is faster but less semantically rich since it is based on a bag-of-words model. Note that the heavy computations occur offline during training, so online responses remain instantaneous using precomputed data structures. The Gold recommender serves the 2 million most connected research products, with the Silver recommender handling the rest (10M), as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Recommender Router.

Category-to-Item Recommender

To tackle the challenge of helping users navigate extensive collections of research products, we developed a category-to-item recommender system that enables dynamic exploration while continuously adapting based on user feedback.

We introduced a two-level exploration framework that operates simultaneously: users specify a broad research area of interest, and in response, our system recommends K Field-of-Science (FoS) tags alongside N research products for each tag, resulting in N x K recommendations. This joint exploration enables users to explore a range of thematic directions while also engaging with specific research products within each direction.

To make the system responsive and adaptive, we implemented a multi-armed bandit strategy that refines recommendations in both levels over time, balancing the discovery of new options with the reinforcement of those already shown to be engaging.

A key contribution of our work is the personalized selection of FoS tags, which guides users through a structured yet flexible exploration process. This personalization streamlines the experience by narrowing the user's interests before delving into specific research products.

Inference of RAIDs via RDGraph analysis

The work undertaken to infer Research Activity Identifiers (RAIDs) from the OpenAIRE Graph involved the development and implementation of algorithms to automatically identify and create RAiD records based on existing research entities and their relationships within the graph. The aim was to discover "potential" RAIDs within the RDGraph by applying pattern mining, graph mining, and machine learning techniques. In this task OPENAIRE contributed to the design, whereas CNR played a significant role in by implementing the algorithm for the inference of RAiD records and their integration into the RDGraph pipeline. Furthermore, CNR also maintained and updated the mapping from the internal RDGraph model towards the RDA's SKG-IF data model, which likely facilitated the representation and interoperability of these newly inferred RAIDs. As a result of these developments, the OpenAIRE Graph, in one of its past releases, introduced approximately 30,000 Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) records inferred from its content, representing research activities as groups of scientific results on the same topics, research projects (grants) that funded them as well as the research organizations involved.

The workflow that drives the creation of RAiD entities from the OpenAIRE Graph consists in 4 phases:

1. Documents creation

This phase transforms the graph entities involved in the RAiDs into documents by using both entity (i.e. attributes) and graph properties (i.e. semantic relationships). The documents are composed by the following words:

- ⦿ The research product language
- ⦿ The research product subjects (i.e. the FOS subjects, to have a curated view)
- ⦿ The research product country
- ⦿ The project producing the research product
- ⦿ The organizations involved in the research product
- ⦿ A label describing the graph clique of the projects (i.e. research products in the same clique obtained after the mesh closure of the relationships with projects shares this label)
- ⦿ A label describing the graph clique of the organizations (i.e. research products in the same clique obtained after the mesh closure of HasAuthorInstitutionOf relationships)
- ⦿ A label describing the graph clique of the versions (i.e. research products in the same clique obtained after the mesh closure of isVersionOf relationships)
- ⦿ A label describing the graph clique of the parts (i.e. research products in the same clique obtained after the mesh closure of HasPart relationships)
- ⦿ A label describing the graph clique of the supplements (i.e. research products in the same clique obtained after the mesh closure of isSupplementedBy relationships)

2. Embeddings creation

This phase transforms the documents to vectors. The vector generation is performed using the Word2Vec of Apache Spark, configured to extract 128-sized embeddings. The more two documents are similar (i.e. share the same labels) the closer (i.e. based on euclidean distance) are their embeddings in the 128-dimensional space.

3. Proximity clustering

This phase performs an approximate similarity join of the embeddings to draw similarity relationships between the embeddings having euclidean distance lower than 0.1. Such similarity relationships are consequently filtered by keeping only those relationships between products sharing at least 3 authors and having dates within a span of 3 years.

Once the final set of similarity relationships is available, the meshes are closed and the Raw RAiD entities are created.

The idea behind the approximate similarity join is to perform a cross-join based on hash tables, to prevent comparing all the entities with all the others, as only entities in the same hash bucket are compared.

4. AI generation

This phase transforms the Raw RAiD entities to the final version of RAiD entities.

Once the Raw RAiD entities have been prepared, an LLM model generates the title and the description of each entity having as input the list of the titles and the descriptions in the Raw RAiD entity.

The generation is performed with the following prompt:

“You are an assistant aimed at generating a JSON with title and description for a research activity based on the given article titles and descriptions.

Format the response in JSON like this:

```
{ "title": "a title of max 10 words for the research activity", "description": "a brief abstract of min 40 and max 150 words that describes the research activity" }
```

Make sure to fill the JSON fields with the required information, and not to exactly repeat the title in the description.”

3.1.2.3 RDGraph Portals

3.1.2.3.1 Discovery portal

The discovery portal is the user interface that allows users to search, discover and navigate through the contents of the RDGraph either with keyword or natural language search. The RDGraph Portal integrates a suite of APIs to provide a comprehensive and user-centric discovery experience. It must communicate with a search API that supports both keyword-based and filter-based queries, as well as natural language search capabilities, enabling users to retrieve relevant results from the RDGraph efficiently.

Keyword search

Provides both simple and advanced search interfaces that enable users to explore the contents of the RDGraph by entering keywords. These interfaces interact with a dedicated Search Service, which queries the Solr Index containing RDGraph data.

Figure 6 - Screenshot of the main search UI of the RDGraph portal.

Figure 7 - Screenshot of the advanced search.

Search results are presented to users with options for refinement and sorting based on relevance, publication date, title, and was enhanced with impact-based indicators, including citation count, impulse (recent citation count), popularity (AttRank), and influence (PageRank).

Figure 8 - A search result showing impact indicators.

Figure 9 - The options for ranking search results.

Among other search capabilities, the RDGraph portal further supports searching by Software Heritage IDs (T6.3).

Figure 10 - Example of a search using Software Heritage IDs.

Natural Language Search

The RDGraph Portal introduces dedicated pages for the Natural Language Search functionality that transforms the way users interact with complex research data. Instead of requiring technical expertise or knowledge of query languages, users can now simply ask questions in everyday language, just as they would ask a colleague, and receive meaningful, structured answers. This capability is powered by advanced AI techniques that translate natural language questions into precise database queries in real time (as described in T3.3). Whether a user wants to find the how many papers are written in each language, or which publisher has the most papers on a specific subject, they can do so without needing to understand the underlying data structure. They write their question in the provided form and the system intelligently interprets the intent of each question, retrieves the most relevant information from the RDGraph, and presents it in a user-friendly format. This functionality is made possible through integration with a dedicated Natural Language Search Service, based on a Large Language Model (LLM). It not only simplifies access to valuable insights but also empowers a broader audience to explore the rich data within RDGraph.

Figure 11 - Main UI of the NL search.

Figure 12 - Results of the NL Search.

3.1.2.3.2 Management of Community Profiles

The goal of this task is to deliver the results of the intelligent services developed in T3.3 to end users, supporting more effective navigation of the RDGraph. As the volume of research products continues to grow, identifying relevant content becomes increasingly challenging. To address this, personalized recommendations are provided to help users discover research products that align with their interests, content that might otherwise remain undiscovered. To showcase the capabilities of these intelligent services

and make them accessible to end users, enabling them to fully benefit, the RDGraph portal has either introduced new pages to display the output of the underlying tools or enhanced existing ones with the added-value information they provide. There are three possible types of recommendations. For each type, we describe both the functionality it offers and how the RDGraph portal ensures it is both accessible and clearly presented to users.

Researcher-centric

These recommendations are available to end users upon login with their ORCID, in the home page of the RDGraph portal. They are based on the User-to-Item Recommender (described in T3.3) that recommends publications based on citation behavior within research communities. Users will receive personalized suggestions of research publications based on their citation behavior and the citation patterns of others within their research community. These recommendations aim to highlight relevant research outputs—such as journal articles, papers, or other scholarly works—that the user may find valuable but might not have discovered on their own. This functionality is enabled whenever users login with their ORCID.

Figure 13 - Screenshot of the researcher-centric recommender.

Research field-specific

The Research field-specific recommendations are based on the Category-to-Item Recommender (described in T3.3) and have their own dedicated page. From this page, users can view and select all the communities that have recommendations. Users select the community of their interest and the recommendations are presented to them by relevant community topics. For the top 3 topics of the selected communities, the top 6 recommendations are presented to the users. Currently the available communities that users can select are: Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage, Energy Research, EO SC and Transport Research.

Figure 14 - Screenshot of the field-specific recommender.

Similarity-based

These recommendations are available in the landing pages of the research products, and are presented in a special "Recommended" tab. There users can view and access the top recommended research products similar to the current one. They are based on the Item-to-Item Recommender (described in T3.3).

Figure 15 - Screenshot of the similarity-based recommender.

3.1.2.3.3 Creation and validation of RAiDs

RAiDs (Research Activity Identifiers) provide structured, persistent, and machine-actionable identifiers for comprehensive research activities. These clusters are designed to encapsulate the full lifecycle and context of a research endeavor by systematically grouping related research outputs—such as publications, datasets, software—alongside associated research activities (e.g., funded projects) and the contributing organizations and individuals.

In the RDGraph portal, RAiDs act as conceptual containers that enable users to understand not just individual outputs, but the broader research narrative they are part of. This holistic representation fosters improved traceability, impact assessment, and reuse across scientific communities.

To identify and construct these clusters, the RDGraph employs graph-based machine learning algorithms such as Metapath2Vec and DeepWalk. These algorithms analyze the existing semantic relationships among entities in the RDGraph—such as co-authorship, funding links, thematic similarity, and institutional affiliation—to infer and suggest meaningful RAiD groupings. This data-driven approach enhances the accuracy and scalability of RAiD creation, especially in large, interconnected datasets.

The RDGraph portal offers a dedicated user interface for exploring these Research Activity clusters. Users can perform targeted searches, navigate detailed views of RAiD-associated entities, and explore the interconnections that define a research activity. Each RAiD cluster page visualizes the aggregated research ecosystem, helping users make sense of complex collaborations and outputs.

Figure 16 - Searching for research activities.

Impaired Src signaling and post-synaptic actin polymerization in Alzheimer's disease

Summary **RAiD Research product Parts (48)** RAID Project Parts (50) RAID Organization Parts (209) Metrics Recommended

Research activities are inferred by OpenAIRE. They are organized by grouping related research derived from the OpenAIRE Graph based on shared attributes such as authors, topics, and collaborations. Advanced AI techniques, including clustering and large language models (LLMs), are used to identify connections, refine groupings, and generate clear titles and descriptions, making it easier to explore and understand research efforts.

48 Research Products, Page 1 of 5

Regenerative Models for the Integration and Regeneration of Head Skeletal Tissues

Publication » Article • 2018 • Publisher: MDPI AG • Funded by: NIH | The function of chromatin...

Authors: Warren A. Vieira; Catherine D. McCusker;

DOI: 10.3390/ijms19123752 PMID: 30486286 PMC: PMC6321600

Disease of, or trauma to, the human jaw account for thousands of reconstructive surgeries performed every year. One of the most popular and successful treatment options in this context involves the transplantation of bone tissue from a different anatomical region into the affected jaw. Although, this...

International Journals... Link to Share Cite Access Routes

Figure 17 - An example recommended RAiD.

Additionally, the portal provides a promotional message to facilitate the onboarding of inferred RAiDs into the official RAiD registry. This feature encourages the validation and registration of automatically inferred RAiDs, bridging the gap between inference and persistent identification, and promoting wider adoption of RAiDs within the EOSC and beyond.

Figure 18 - UI to redirect to RAiD registration.

3.1.3 Code & resources availability

URL	Description	License
https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dhp-schemas	OpenAIRE Graph model reference classes	GNU AGPLv3
https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop	OpenAIRE Graph framework project, documentation available at https://graph.openaire.eu/docs	GNU AGPLv3
https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop/src/branch/main/dhp-workflows/dhp-aggregation	Metadata collection workflows	GNU AGPLv3
https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop/src/branch/main/dhp-workflows/dhp-impact-indicators	Impact indicators workflow	GNU AGPLv3
https://github.com/athenarc/Bip-Ranker	Impact indicators algorithms	GNU GPLv2
https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dhp-graph-dump	Project defining the workflows for creating & publishing the OpenAIRE Graph dump, including the RDGraph one	GNU AGPLv3
https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dhp-dump-schema	Project defining the reference classes of the different public datasets created from the OpenAIRE Graph, including the RDGraph	
https://github.com/athenarc/fc4eosc-nlsearch	NL search	
https://github.com/athenarc/fc4eosc-recommender	Community recommendation	
https://code-repo.d4science.org/michele.debonis/raid-inference	Project implementing the RAiD inference algorithms	GNU AGPLv3
https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop/src/branch/main/dhp-workflows/dhp-aggregation	Project implementing the data integration layer used to import the inferred RAiDs in the OpenAIRE Graph	GNU AGPLv3
https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/faircore4eosc-explore/src/branch/main/README.md	The RDGraph portal documentation	
https://code-repo.d4science.org/MaDgIK/faircore4eosc-explore	Project implementing the RDGraph portal	Apache 2.0

Table 1 - List of RDGraph-related code repositories.

3.2 The EOSC PID Graph Service (PIDGraph)

3.2.1 Component Overview

The PIDGraph services are designed to facilitate the exposure and usage of Persistent Identifier (PID) metadata and connections, centered around a trusted source - in this instance, the core data of the graph is made up of Digital Object Identifier (DOI) metadata held by DataCite, one of the main DOI Registration Agencies (RAs), and the network of the graph is built around the relationships connection one DOI to another, and also outwards from DOIs to other established and trusted PIDs within the research community, including Open Researcher and Contributor IDs (ORCiDs) for people, and Research Organisation Registry (ROR) identifiers for institutions, as well as domain specific persistent identifiers such as zbMATH Article Identifiers.

The genesis of the PIDGraph was the FREYA project which ran from December 2017 until December 2020, during which the initial versions of some of the PIDGraph services were developed and deployed. In May 2020, a production service of a GraphQL API was launched to enable queries of the new PIDGraph, and this was followed by the release of a graphical web interface called DataCite Commons in October 2020.

During the FAIRCORE4EOSC (FC4E) project, the main aims were to enhance the stability and functionality of the PIDGraph services, to expand the quantity of data available in the graph, and to develop new methods of accessing and interacting with the PIDGraph.

This took the form of several distinct components:

- PIDGraph extensions – increasing the range of data exposed and access methods of the graph, aiming towards increased FAIRness and compatibility with other Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs)
- PID Link Claims – a method for external sources of PID information to provide new data to be ingested into the graph
- Data Usage Statistics – integration of COUNTER (Counting Online Usage of Networked Electronic Resources) compliant statistics for data access and usage provided by DataCite members into the PIDGraph
- PIDGraph Data Dumps – regular generation of data files comprising the entirety of the PIDGraph data, for use in bootstrapping other SKGs and services, and analysis across the entire graph

Figure 19 offers a high-level overview of the data flow through the PIDGraph services.

Figure 19- A diagram showing the data flow through the PIDGraph services

3.2.2 Design & development

3.2.2.1 PIDGraph

During the early phases of the project, work on the main PIDGraph component was focused in two areas – firstly, the gathering of user requirements and desires for functionality and data available within the PIDGraph, and secondly on enhancing the underlying infrastructure and services that underpin all PIDGraph related outputs.

A key element of this phase was a collaborative discovery process, led by DataCite, to better understand the needs of stakeholders engaging with PIDGraph outputs. This included a series of focus group sessions with project partners and broader community stakeholders to surface user needs, identify common pain points, and prioritize desired features. Insights from these sessions directly informed the development of initial product specifications. Particular attention was given to the usability of the PIDGraph, data quality expectations, and the types of relationships and metadata that users would find most valuable when visualizing or querying the PIDGraph.

It was expected that the scale of data within the graph would expand dramatically during the lifetime of FC4E, as a function of the increased number of DOI registrations along with integration of new or existing PIDs either underpinned by DOIs or transitioning to be so (for example Research Activity Identifiers–RAIDs–and International Generic Sample Numbers–IGSNs–respectively) increasing the amount of nodes within the graph, and the PID Link Claims component providing extra vertices from the core of the graph out to other nodes.

Additionally, the planned integrations with other components developed during FC4E, and increased levels of access and querying from both new and existing users of the data meant that the demand on the PIDGraph services was highly likely to scale more rapidly than the design of the service had previously accommodated.

This made it essential that the underlying infrastructure was both modernised and future-proofed, and as a consequence, during the early phases of FC4E, a large amount of work was undertaken towards these aims.

Almost all of the PIDGraph outputs relied on an ElasticSearch service under-the-hood at some point in their operation, and so this was initially upgraded to the latest major version and then subsequently through the available minor versions until the service was running on the most recent available release of the software. Alongside this, experimentation was done on how various types of data indexing and querying affected the speed and resilience of the service, leading to an additional upgrade in the hardware capacity of the servers providing the service.

Following on from the Beta Release Milestone of FC4E, significant further upgrade work took place to move the service from ElasticSearch to the OpenSearch fork, in order to provide access to newer features required by the development of other services within the PIDGraph, such as Point-In-Time searching. At the same time, the database service utilised by the PIDGraph was given a major upgrade from MySQL 5 to MySQL 8.

In the latter phase of FC4E, development on the core PIDGraph services consisted of enhancements to the various methods of accessing the graph data via APIs and frontend services. This included extensive work to update the underlying frameworks and libraries, with significant upgrades including porting the code behind the REST API, GraphQL API, and Event Data API to both the next major version of Ruby, and also the latest version of the Ruby on Rails framework used by all of these services.

```

1 {
2   organization(id: "https://ror.org/04wxnsj81") {
3     id
4     name
5     works(hasViews: 100, first: 100) {
6       nodes {
7         id
8         type
9         publisher {
10          name
11        }
12        publicationYear
13        titles {
14          title
15        }
16        creators {
17          id
18          name
19          affiliation {
20            id
21            name
22          }
23        }
24        citationCount
25        viewCount
26        downloadCount
27      }
28    }
29  }
30 }

```

```

{
  "data": {
    "organization": {
      "id": "https://ror.org/04wxnsj81",
      "name": "DataCite",
      "works": {
        "nodes": [
          {
            "id": "https://
            handle.stage.datacite.org/10.70048/
            findable101",
            "type": "Dataset",
            "publisher": {
              "name": "DataCite e.V."
            },
            "publicationYear": 2016,
            "titles": [
              {
                "title": "DataCite Metadata
                Schema Documentation for the Publication and
                Citation of Research Data v4.0"
              }
            ],
            "creators": [
              {
                "id": null,
                "name": "DataCite Metadata
                Working Group",
                "affiliation": []
              }
            ],
            "citationCount": 0,
            "viewCount": 181,

```

Figure 20 - An example query in the GraphQL API, demonstrating the ability to search by PID, and retrieve a selected subset of metadata for the node, as well as metadata from connected nodes.

To improve queryability of the data and the responsiveness of those queries, extra data fields and aggregations were exposed via the REST API, as well as the addition of further filtering capability to promote the interoperability with other FC4E components and services.

One example of this is the capability added to enable simple discovery of the DOIs and metadata that underpins the RAiD service developed within FC4E. With the addition of this filter, it becomes possible for external services integrating with the PIDGraph to easily identify RAiDs and restrict queries to just those DOIs, lowering the barrier to interoperability of integration and enhancements to wider services built on top of PIDGraph capabilities.

Figure 21 - A search in DataCite Commons filtered to only return results from RAiD Registries.

Significant refactoring was performed on the DataCite Commons frontend, with the display of connections to other PIDs within the graph enhanced to include more options for traversing through the graph in a simple, visual manner. Additions were made to the graph visualisations included on individual node display pages, such as the provision of a force-directed network graph providing an intuitive representation of the types of nodes connected to the node being viewed.

Type to search...

Works People Organizations Repositories

Pages - Support Sign In

Hakai Institute Juvenile Salmon Program Time Series <https://doi.org/10.48321/d1cw23>

26 Citations

Add to ORCID Record

Download Metadata

Cite as

Johnson, B. (2024). *Hakai Institute Juvenile Salmon Program Time Series*. DMPTool. <https://doi.org/10.48321/D1CW23>

APA

Download Reports

Related Works (CSV)

Share

- Email
- Twitter
- Facebook

Description Creators Contributors Funders Registration

The Hakai Institute Juvenile Salmon program is an ongoing initiative that was established in 2015 in partnership with the University of British Columbia, University of Toronto, Simon Fraser University and Salmon Coast Field Station. This program researches the early life history of juvenile salmon in coastal British Columbia. Primary research objectives are determining: 1) Migration timing rates and routes; 2) Migration habitat, including physical and chemical oceanographic conditions, and availability of plankton prey; 3) The impacts of prey phenology, quantity and quality on juvenile salmon growth and condition; 4) Species and stock-specific feeding biology and competitive interactions; 5) Pathogen and parasite infection dynamics; and 6) Mortality estimates. The program targets Fraser River sockeye, and pink and chum salmon, but additionally provides information on coho, chinook, and herring through incidental capture. The field program operates between May and July during the peak of the juvenile sockeye outward migration. Purse seine and oceanographic sampling are conducted in the northern Strait of Georgia / Discovery Islands region (~ 220 km from the Fraser River mouth).

Data Management Plan published 2024 in California Digital Library

Output Management Plan English

<https://doi.org/10.48321/d1cw23>

Related Works

Filter Works

Type to search...

Connection Types

- References 36
- Citations 27
- Other 1

Creators & Contributors

- Hunt, Brian P. V. 11
- Johnson, Brett 6
- Gan, Julian C.L. 3
- Suttle, Curtis A. 3
- Pakhomov, E. A. 3
- Rogers, Luke A. 3
- Waterman, Stephanie 2
- Krkosek, Martin 2
- Mordecai, Gideon J 2
- van der Stap, Tim 2

Figure 22 - The DataCite Commons page for a Data Management Plan, showing the visual representations of connections through the graph.

Figure 23 - The DataCite Commons page for one of the contributors involved in the Data Management Plan shown in the previous figure.

3.2.2.2 PID Link Claims

A significant utility is gained by the PIDGraph services in expanding the data comprising the graph, both in terms of addition of additional nodes to the graph, but also in making new connections from nodes in the graph to each other, and also to external nodes identified by PIDs that are beyond the current scope of the graph.

The PID Link Claims component was designed to provide a mechanism for the PIDGraph to ingest the latter of these, by the development of additional Agents that collect relationships between PIDs into the Event Data service that is the underlying data store of vertices within the graph.

During FC4E, the capability for ingesting new PID Links from compatible OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) servers was developed. Working closely with partners from FIZ Karlsruhe, representing the Mathematics Case Study through the zbMATH Open and swMATH portals, a collaborative iteration on mapping the zbMATH and swMATH schemas to the DataCite Metadata Schema was performed during the second half of the project.

Guided by a dedicated series of virtual meetings, and in-person workshop sessions, the team from FIZ Karlsruhe produced an initial mapping in the form of an XSLT (Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformation) and with feedback from the DataCite team on the output and refinements that could be made, continued to produce a series of new versions of the mapping, working towards full support for all of the fields available in the DataCite Metadata Schema for which the zbMATH and swMATH services held data.

Simultaneously, development work by the DataCite team created a pair of ingest agents, one for each portal's records, that were capable of harvesting the records from the FIZ Karlsruhe OAI-PMH server, and extracting the relevant relationships for the PIDGraph. These agents were implemented as part of the existing Event Data service, to sit alongside the ingestion of PID↔PID links exposed by other DOI RAs.

The ingest agents identify new vertices that have a connection to one or more existing nodes in the graph, and parse out the relevant metadata to add to the PIDGraph service, ensuring it is surfaced through multiple

methods of access, and that critical information such as previously unknown citations and references to datasets improves the coverage of the graph, and increases the accuracy of citation metrics displayed throughout the graph, as well as further downstream in the community by making these available to third parties using the PIDGraph data to enhance their own local graphs and metadata holdings.

A significant achievement from the PID Link Claims component work is the inclusion into the PIDGraph for the first time of zbMATH Document Identifiers for research outputs in the field of Mathematics, making an identifier with an almost 200 year history available as part of the wider graph and enhancing the functionality of the PIDGraph by leveraging the trusted record of citations curated by the zbMATH service. A sample dataset of the new relationship data imported from zbMATH was published on Zenodo [R3].

Figure 24 - A graph showing the increase in the vertices contained within the PIDGraph over the lifetime of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

3.2.2.3 Data Usage Statistics

The DataCite Usage Statistics service provides information on the number of views and downloads for individual DOIs following the COUNTER code of practice⁵. Usage data is collected through two primary methods: by allowing DataCite member repositories to embed the Usage Tracker code⁶ on their landing pages or by accepting submissions via the Usage Report API.⁷ Once collected, the data is made available through DataCite Commons and the PID Graph for broader discovery and reuse.

This service was initially developed with support from the Make Data Count⁸ (MDC) initiative. As part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, we enhanced the underlying infrastructure to support greater scalability and

⁵ <https://cop5.projectcounter.org/>

⁶ <https://support.datacite.org/docs/datacite-usage-tracker>

⁷ <https://support.datacite.org/docs/usage-reports-api-guide>

⁸ <https://makedatacount.org/>

integration. We are now collaborating with the GREI⁹ project to encourage participating DataCite member repositories to contribute usage data, further enhancing the richness and value of the service.

While this service is designed for DataCite members to contribute usage data, the resulting statistics are openly accessible to the broader community for querying and integration into other platforms.

Figure 25 - Views and download counts for DataCite DOIs from CERN.

3.2.2.4 PIDGraph Data Dumps

The design of the PIDGraph Data Dumps service focused on providing a complete output of all of the data available within the graph, in a manner that made it suitable for both bootstrapping another graph or including the PIDGraph data wholesale, but also for targeted extraction of specific records, providing methods for local data enhancement and analysis outside of the framework of these functionalities provided by the core PIDGraph services.

The first iteration of the PIDGraph data file was prepared for the Beta Release Milestone of the project, utilising the existing REST API code to provide serialisation of DOI metadata in a format identical to the REST API response, which was then split into files of 1000 records each and compressed using gzip.

Whilst this approach met the requirements of providing a copy of the PIDGraph data for external use, following internal evaluation and discussion, as well as feedback from the Case Studies and Demonstrators in FC4E, the decision was taken to rework both the generation code, in order to decrease the time and resources required to generate the data file, and also to modify the output format to make it easier to perform targeted extraction and analysis of the data.

⁹ <https://datascience.nih.gov/data-ecosystem/generalist-repository-ecosystem-initiative>

For the second iteration of the data file, the generator code was rewritten separately from the REST API code into a dedicated service of its own. This brought many advantages, including the ability to multi-thread the code and switch to a job-based model of generation, allowing significant parallelisation of the process and a speed increase from the generation taking several days to only taking several hours.

At the same time, the data format underwent a significant modification, with the most significant change being a switch to JSONLines, meaning that each file contained one whole JSON document per line. This enabled the data file to be parsed as a stream of individual records, rather than having to read and parse each thousand-record chunk as a single JSON document before being able to query or filter it. Based on internal testing, this change reduced the time required to iterate over the data file and extract a targeted set of records (in this instance, all records containing an author with an affiliation to a specific institution) to less than an hour. Another change in the second version of the data file was that the records were bucketed into folders based on the prefix of the DOI, to provide enhanced support for consumers of the data file who were only interested in retrieving a specific set of records.

The changes aided in lowering the barrier to using the graph data and providing greater support for identified use cases within FC4E such as producing a subset graph for specific domains or research produced within a certain country. Further testing and integration pilots were performed with a variety of stakeholders, and this led to several presentations at the euroCRIS 2024 conference, and a co-authored paper with CSC/Research.fi¹⁰ on the piloting of PIDGraph data for use with a national level CRIS system [R4].

The second iteration of the file was released publicly in March 2024 as the first production release of the PIDGraph Data Dump component output, containing 52,863,283 records of DOI metadata, totalling 197GiB of files [R5].

To further meet use cases arising from FC4E, a second data file was produced, the PID Links data file, containing metadata about the vertices in the graph. This dataset allows users who wish to analyse connections between PIDs, for example to enrich locally held data on research outputs with a list of citations and references, to do so in an efficient manner. The specific nature of the data format - at its core, a triple containing the two related PIDs and the type of relationship, alongside additional metadata about the relationship, such as the date of occurrence and provenance of the relationship assertion - enables consumers to retrieve this connection information without the added overhead of parsing the entirety of the metadata for each record. In addition, the PID Links file contained assertions of connections between nodes that originated from secondary sources, including other DOI RAs, leading to a significantly richer view of the graph of wider scholarly outputs.

The first production version of the PID Links file was released in June 2024 containing records for 167,844,248 relationships between PIDs in the graph and totalling 95GiB of data [R6].

Following the releases of the first production versions of the PIDGraph data files, a further round of feedback and iteration was undertaken, with insights from a wide variety of stakeholders, both internal to the FC4E project, and external stakeholders from the wider scholarly community providing valuable guidance on enhancing the utility of the data files.

This feedback led to additional changes to the format of the main PIDGraph data file, with the inclusion of additional data in each record, as well as a CSV file listing all DOIs within a bucket, including those with the status of Registered, allowing the data file to also reflect DOIs that have been “withdrawn” (as a persistent identifier, a DOI is never deleted, but in instances such as incorrect publication, their metadata can be removed from publicly available sources - see <https://support.datacite.org/docs/doi-states>).

¹⁰ <http://research.fi/>

Additional changes were made to the structure and packaging of the data file, including moving the gzip compression to be performed on the individual JSONLines files rather than the whole archive, which enables faster decompression in parallel, as well as increasing the number of records in each file to 10,000, and changing the bucketing to be done by the last updated date of the record.

This third iteration was released as the second production release of the PIDGraph data file in January 2025, and comprises 72,019,577 records totalling 347GiB of data [R7].

Following the end of FC4E, it is planned to continue releasing data files of the PIDGraph data on a yearly basis, and to further enhance the interoperability of the PIDGraph data file outputs with other Scholarly Knowledge Graph services.

3.2.3 Code & resources availability

URL	Description	Documentation
https://api.datacite.org	REST API endpoint	https://support.datacite.org/docs/api
https://api.datacite.org/graphql	GraphQL API endpoint	https://support.datacite.org/docs/datacite-graphql-api-guide
https://datafiles.datacite.org	Data Files Portal containing PIDGraph data dumps	https://support.datacite.org/docs/datacite-public-data-file
https://api.datacite.org/events?source_id=zbmath_related	Event Data API endpoint	https://support.datacite.org/docs/eventdata-guide
https://commons.datacite.org	DataCite Commons web frontend to the graph	https://support.datacite.org/docs/datacite-commons
https://github.com/datacite/lupo	REST + GraphQL APIs code	
https://github.com/datacite/levriero	PID Links agents code	
https://github.com/datacite/saluki	Data Files Portal code	
https://github.com/datacite/keeshond	Data Usage Statistics code	

Table 2 - List of PIDGraph-related code repositories.

4 Demonstrators

4.1 Introduction and background

EUDAT's discovery service B2FIND evaluated how to improve the discoverability of B2FIND datasets on B2FIND and EOSC level by exchanging metadata with PID and RD Graph. Contrary to the case-studies implementations under WP7, the Demonstrators are conceived outside the immediate context of a specific research community, but work closer with the service development teams. The Demonstrator implementations should all be considered as useful beyond the added value aspect for the B2FIND service, since it serves as blueprint and possible example for other services intending to make use of and integrate with the graph services RDGraph and PIDGraph.

The work was split into three subtasks: Integration of B2FIND metadata into the RDGraph, B2FIND exposure of metadata to Open Knowledge Graphs, and PIDGraph metadata integration in B2FIND. Each subtask is described below with related software, achievements and how they are demonstrated, as well as the benefits across the components. In addition, also further relations and links to FC4E and EUDAT services are integrated in the B2FIND service as shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26 - B2FIND relations to FC4E services.

The Demonstrator task has an associated Milestone MS16 "Software and demos of the demonstrator outcome in WP3" which reports on the state of the demonstrator task and the achievements in M24, when the task 3.6 was finalised. In particular, we describe the software repositories and demo of integration workflow and its benefits across B2FIND, RDGraph, PIDGraph, and other Scientific Knowledge Graphs.

The status of the Demonstrators 3.6 and 4.5 was presented and discussed in the technical meeting in Athens May 23-25 2024 and proposed priorities were discussed and agreed. In addition, at the EUDAT Conference in Karlsruhe, December 3-5 2024, FAIRCORE4EOSC contributions to EUDAT service development and benefits for research communities in general were presented and discussed¹¹.

¹¹ FAIRCORE4EOSC contributions to EUDAT service development <https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/YmibmTz4d2xNosz?dir=undefined&path=%2FDay%203%20-%20205%20Dec%2F0930A%20FAIRCORE4EOSC%20contributions%20to%20EUDAT%20Services&openfile=79970309>

4.2 The Demonstrator subtasks

4.2.1 B2FIND Integration into RDGraph

Following the OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives¹² the main results are:

Incremental and stable ingestion workflow comprising

1. Mapping of B2FIND records to oai_datacite format
2. Exposure of xml files encoded in oai_datacite via B2FIND OAI-PMH extension
3. Harvesting of records by OpenAIRE and subsequent indexing in the OpenAIRE RDGraph

During the integration of all B2FIND records in the OpenAIRE RDGraph, the mapping of the resource type of research products in B2FIND was improved for better compatibility with the OpenAIRE Guidelines. B2FIND also extended the exposure of metadata information to instruments and a second-level provenance of the metadata, i.e. exporting information about the original source repository the metadata in case of harvesting from an aggregator catalogue. This of course highly depends on the quality and richness of the harvested metadata.

The additional exposed and harvested metadata fields are only partly indexed and discoverable in the RDGraph due to other search facet priorities of the discovery portals. For some cases of interest (e.g., metadata related to instruments) it will be investigated whether the RDGraph is appropriate to accommodate this type of metadata, since the current focus is rather on supporting metadata that can be mapped to the SKG-IF specification for Scientific Knowledge Graphs which is of significant importance for EOSC.

The integration of B2FIND into the RDGraph yields benefits for both users of B2FIND and the RDGraph and thus EOSC: The data pool of the RD Graph and with it the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub are enriched with curated metadata, including data sources exclusively harvested by B2FIND. Researchers are able to discover research products harvested from B2FIND also from RDGraph and the EOSC EU Node, leading to enhanced data discovery possibilities as one prerequisite for data re-use.

Software:

- B2FIND's metadata ingestion code (python scripts) stored in GitHub repository¹³
- OAI provider service based on OAI-PMH CKAN extension installed in B2FIND¹⁴

Demo:

Overall integration of records and resource type mapping is demonstrated by the status as shown in OpenAIRE Explore, the OpenAIRE provider dashboard and aggregation history and the demo instance of the RDGraph.

¹² OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/index.html>

¹³ B2FIND's metadata ingestion source code : <https://github.com/EUDAT-B2FIND/md-ingestion/tree/master/mdingestion>

¹⁴ B2FIND's OAI-PMH Extension for CKAN : <https://github.com/EUDAT-B2FIND/ckanext-oaipmh-server>

Figure 27 - Ingestion of B2FIND metadata into RDGraph.

B2FIND exposure of metadata to Open Knowledge Graphs

4.2.2 B2FIND exposure of metadata to Open Knowledge Graphs

This demonstrator task intends the exchange of metadata from B2FIND's metadata catalogue with Open Knowledge Graphs. This will be implemented by exchange of the metadata via the SKG-IF Interoperability Framework.¹⁵

Given the rudimentary maturity of SKG-IF, we opted to implement a different set of EOSC IF guidelines, specifically the OpenAIRE Guidelines, to integrate B2FIND with the EOSC Knowledge Graph. This is covered by the integration activity 'B2FIND Integration into RDGraph' described above. Thus, we postponed the implementation of detailed mappings from B2FIND metadata to SKG-IF entities until a stable version of the framework will be available. As of today, the SKG-IF has reached a first consensus-based form. We are working on refining and enhancing the crosswalk from B2FIND to the SKG-IF model,¹⁶ in order to enable interoperability with other SKGs, including PID Graph and EOSC Knowledge Graph. Compliance with the SKG-IF model will be an important consideration for planned B2FIND software stack updates. An Initial definition of a crosswalk between B2FIND metadata and SKG-IF model entities has been drafted.¹⁷

We expect from this integration benefits for B2FIND and Knowledge Graphs, in particular that B2FIND metadata gain visibility across OpenAIRE, Scopus, EOSC, and other OSGs that are enriched by retrieving

¹⁵ SKG-IF <https://skg-if.github.io/>

¹⁶ SKGs modelled entities

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1m8vQkklLWmDYk55oI6YxZcqkvL7CHp385stjlyy-5m/>

¹⁷ https://github.com/EUDAT-B2FIND/md-ingestion/blob/fc4e_demos/mdingestion/writer/skg.py

metadata from B2FIND via SKG-IF. This leads ultimately to extended discoverability of B2FIND research products.

4.2.3 PIDGraph metadata integration in B2FIND

The aim of this demonstrator subtask was to investigate the integration of information from the PIDGraph to enrich B2FIND metadata. The B2FIND team chose two implementations for demonstration:

- retrieve and display information on the citations of a given dataset in B2FIND dataset display and
- provide links to RAiD (Research Activity Identifier) information that leads researchers to more information about the research project the dataset is associated with.

We implemented the use cases 'citationCount' and associated links to the citations by retrieving the information from PIDGraph via its graphql API.¹⁸ For details how the retrieving of these metadata from PIDGraph is coded see the Jupyter notebook.¹⁹ A badge 'citation'²⁰ displays the citationCount of the research product in the B2FIND demo instance, whereas links to related identifiers that are citing the dataset can be found in the Related Identifier section of the search result page with relationType 'IsCitedBy', as shown in the figure below and in the B2FIND dataset sample.²¹

Figure 28 - PIDGraph citation count information integrated in B2FIND search result.

The usecase 'RAiD info' is implemented by providing links to test-RAiD information in the Identifier section indicated with the relation type 'hasRAiD' as shown in the figure below and in the B2FIND dataset sample.²²

¹⁸ PIDGraph's qlquery API: <https://api.datacite.org/graphql>

¹⁹ Jupyter notebook: https://gitlab.dkrz.de/k204019/metacross/-/blob/main/notebooks/PIDGraph_query_citcount.ipynb?ref_type=heads

²⁰ Implementation of badge 'citations': https://github.com/EUDAT-B2FIND/ckanext-b2find/blob/cite_badge/ckanext/b2find/templates/package/snippets/labels.html

²¹ B2FIND sample of dataset with citationCount badge: <http://demo-b2find9.cloud.dkrz.de/dataset/f6153acc-bc57-54a2-b549-63f6f253744c>

²² B2FIND sample of dataset with RAiD metadata: <http://demo-b2find.dkrz.de/dataset/ec1593ab-84d3-565b-83c2-8a42a37a7170>

Core Components Supporting a FAIR EOSC

EOSC Research Activity Identifier Service

<https://app.demo.raid.org.au/raids/10.80360/c4750cdc>

B2FIND datasets connected to related RAiD

Use case: offer links and information on the research activity a dataset is related to

[B2FIND dataset with link to RAiD](#)

IPCC DDC: CAS FGOALS-f3-L model output prepared for CMIP6 GMMIP

These data include the subset used by IPCC AR6 WGI authors of the datasets originally published in ESGF for 'CMIP6 GMMIP/CAS FGOALS-f3-L' with the full Data Reference Syntax following the template: 'rip_era_activity_id institution_id source_id experiment_id table_id variable_id grid_label version'. The FGOALS-f3-L climate model, released in 2017, includes the following components: atmos: FAMIL2.2 (Cubed-sphere, c96, 360 x 180 longitude/latitude; 32 levels, top level 2.16 hPa); land: CLM4.0; ocean: LICOM3.0 (LICOM3.0, tropical primarily 1deg, 360 x 270 longitude/latitude; 30 levels, top grid cell 0-10 m); seaice: CICE4.0. The model was run by the Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100009, China (CAS) in native nominal resolutions: atmos: 100 km, land: 100 km, ocean: 100 km, seaice: 100 km.

CAS	CMIP6	FGOALS-f3-L	GMMIP	IPCC	IPCC AR6	IPCC DDC	climate change
model output							

Identifier	
DOI	https://doi.org/10.26907/WDDCCARS-C6/GM/CASF
Related Identifier	https://doi.org/10.80360/c4750cdc
Metadata Access	https://dmtool.cloud.dkrz.de/raiprovider?verb=GetRecords&metadataPrefix=iso19115&identifier=oa:wdcc.dkrz.era-ise_3956197

The screenshot shows the RAID application interface. It displays a list of 'Related Object #'s (1-5) under the 'Organisations' section. Each object has a 'Link' and a 'Type' (Dataset). The interface also shows 'Descriptions' and 'Categories' for each object. A blue arrow points from the 'Related Identifier' in the B2FIND search result to the RAID application URL.

Figure 29 - PIDGraph RAiD connection in B2FIND search result.

B2FIND benefits from the demonstrated method by enriching its search results with valuable additional information for the B2FIND users.

5 Engagement, communication, and user community reception

5.1 RDGraph

The organisations behind the RDGraph has been working closely with the FAIRCORE4EOSC partners to gather requirements for enhancing the RDGraph, aiming to support the content and needs of selected use cases. This collaborative effort has directly shaped the technical development of RDGraph, particularly in enabling the successful integration of graph-based discovery capabilities aligned with specific disciplinary examples. Throughout the project, the respective partners have actively promoted RDGraph through targeted engagement and dissemination activities. The team has presented its work at conferences, contributed to webinars, and delivered technical sessions in collaboration with project partners and broader research infrastructure communities. These activities have been instrumental in increasing visibility and demonstrating the value of RDGraph as a powerful tool for research discovery and knowledge integration within the EOSC ecosystem. A special activity to mention is the RDGraph beta release workshop that was held as an online workshop involving RDGraph end users and demonstrators presenting the core functionality of the beta release of the RDGraph and get feedback from stakeholders. Similar workshops were held in various events (e.g., the CRIS conference).

5.2 PIDGraph

DataCite has been actively engaging with the FAIRCORE4EOSC partners to gather requirements to expand the PID Graph to support content of selected case studies. This collaborative process directly informed technical developments of the successful integration of PID links from the Mathematics case study. This demonstrates the flexibility and extensibility of the PID Graph in supporting a variety of disciplinary contexts.

Over the past three years, DataCite has actively promoted the PID Graph through a wide range of outreach activities. We have presented our work at various conferences, hosted and participated in webinars and delivered technical workshops organised by the project partners and international conferences. These efforts have been helpful in raising awareness and sharing the potential of the PID Graph as a key component of open research infrastructure.

6 Sustainability

This section offers insights into the sustainability of the two components, complementing the analysis presented in the Exploitation Plan (Deliverable D7.3).

6.1 RDGraph

RDGraph aligns with the broader sustainability and governance plans established by OpenAIRE, under existing agreements that guarantee its continued maintenance, development, and integration within the EOSC ecosystem. This strategic positioning secures RDGraph's long-term availability and relevance as a service supporting research discovery. OpenAIRE commits to transfer RDGraph functionalities into the OpenAIRE Graph so as to ensure its adoption by all Graph consumers, including the EOSC Resource Hub.

6.2 PIDGraph

DataCite is committed to the long-term sustainability and ongoing development of the PID Graph beyond the end of the project. We will maintain and evolve the PID Graph in alignment with the evolving needs of the community.

Access to the PID Graph will remain openly available through multiple ways:

- 🕒 DataCite Commons, which provides a user-friendly interface for users to explore and interact with the graph (<https://commons.datacite.org/>)
- 🕒 APIs, which enables integration into external systems and workflows (<https://support.datacite.org/docs/api>)
- 🕒 Downloadable data file, which supports large-scale analysis and offline use (<https://datafiles.datacite.org/>)

7 Conclusions

The development and deployment of the RDGraph and PIDGraph services represent key achievements of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, delivering advanced components that enhance research discovery and interoperability within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem.

The RDGraph provides a federated search service across diverse repositories and data sources, enriched with graph-based discovery and natural language processing tools. By extending the EOSC Catalogue to include entities such as Research Activity Identifiers (RAiDs), and offering multiple access methods (including APIs, user interfaces, and open data dumps), RDGraph enables both human and machine users to explore and reuse research outputs more effectively.

The PIDGraph facilitates the aggregation and exploration of relationships between persistent identifiers (PIDs) from trusted sources such as ORCID, ROR, DataCite, and Crossref. It supports seamless integration into third-party systems through standardized APIs and downloadable data files and includes a service for generating usage statistics, reinforcing the EOSC's goal of building a connected and transparent research infrastructure.

Both components were developed through an agile, iterative process grounded in early prototyping and continuous feedback from use case leaders and demonstrators. This approach ensured responsiveness to real-world needs and supported the timely release and refinement of beta versions.

Extensive engagement activities—including presentations, workshops, and case study collaborations—were crucial in promoting both components, validating their design, and demonstrating their value to the broader research community.

Looking forward, sustainability is ensured for both services. RDGraph will be maintained and further developed within the OpenAIRE infrastructure, with its functionalities integrated into the OpenAIRE Graph to serve a wider range of EOSC services. The PIDGraph will continue to be supported by DataCite, remaining openly accessible through the DataCite Commons portal, APIs, and downloadable files, and evolving to meet emerging community needs.

References

No	Description/Link
R1	Steck, Harald. Embarrassingly Shallow Autoencoders for Sparse Data. The World Wide Web Conference. 2019.
R2	Ginzburg, Dvir, et al. Self-supervised document similarity ranking via contextualized language models and hierarchical inference. Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: ACL-IJCNLP. 2021.
R3	Bennett M, Azzouz-Thuderoz M, Malla Mohamad S, DataCite, FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure. zbMATH <-> PIDGraph integration demo dataset [Internet]. Zenodo; 2025. Available from: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.15052569
R4	Suominen T, Himanen L, Hellsten L, Bennett M, Buys M. Piloting the use of PIDGraph data in Research.fi. Procedia Computer Science [Internet]. 2024;249:232–42. Available from: http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.069
R5	DataCite. DataCite Public Data File [Internet]. DataCite; 2024. Available from: https://datafiles.datacite.org/datafiles/public-2023
R6	DataCite. DataCite PID Links Data File 2023 [Internet]. DataCite; 2024. Available from: https://datafiles.datacite.org/datafiles/pidlinks-2023
R7	DataCite. DataCite Public Data File 2024 [Internet]. DataCite; 2025. Available from: https://datafiles.datacite.org/datafiles/public-2024

Appendix I. Conceptual Mapping from the OpenAIRE Graph to the RDGraph

Research product

SKG-IF PROPERTY	OPENAIRE Graph PROPERTY	NOTES	COMMENTS
local_identifier	id	the openaire identifier for the result	
identifiers.schema	pid.qualifier.classid	map the pids for the result	
identifiers.value	pid.value		
titles	title.value	maps .the first title with type main title . If no title with type main title is present, maps the first title with type subtitle . If not subtitle is available map the first title	This type in the SKG-IF model is a list of strings. Only one title is mapped to avoid repetitions, since no information on the language of the title is provided in the OA metadata
abstracts	description.value	List of value	Map only the first description found in the graph, no information about the language is present in the graph
product_type	resulttype.classid	publication -> literature; dataset-> research data; software -> research software; other -> other	The OA type mapped in the SKGIF type

topics.topic	concat(topic_____,md5(concat(result.subject.qualifier.schema,result.subject.value)))	List of value	OA does not have Topic as an entity. One way to map them would be to create an identifier for all the subjects harvested whose schema id is different from keyword
topics.provenance.type	subject.dataInfo.provenanceaction.classname		
topics.provenance.trust	subject.dataInfo.trust		
contributions.person	if author has orcid -> md5(concat(author.pid.value,Boolean.TRUE)); if author has orcid_pending -> md5(concat(author.pid.value,Boolean.FALSE)); if author does not have orcid -> md5(concat(result.id , author position in the author list))	Naming convention for temporary ids for authors	
contributions.declared_affiliations	not mappable		
contributions.rank	author.rank		
contributions.roles	not mappable	list of strings in the skgif model	https://credit.niso.org/
manifestations.product_local_type	instance.instancetype.classname		
manifestations.product_local_type_scheme	instance.instancetype.schemename		
manifestations.dates.type	publishing	list of dates. we have only one	
manifestations.dates.value	instance.dateofacceptance		
manifestations.peer-review	if instance.refereed.classid = 0000 -> unavailable 0001 -> peer-reviewed 0002 -> not peer-reviewed		

manifestations.metadata_curation	unavailable		
manifestations.access_rights	if instance.accessRight.classid = OPEN or OPEN DATA or OPEN SOURCE -> open CLOSED -> closed RESTRICTED -> restricted EMBARGO or 12MONTHS or 6MONTHS -> embargo else -> unavailable		
manifestations.license	instance.licence.value		
manifestations.license_scheme	not mappable		
manifestations.url	instance.url	map the first url in the instance	
manifestations.pid	instance.pid	map the first pid in the instance	
manifestations.biblio.issue	journal.issue	for the instances associated to journals	To be sure we map for the correct instance, we need to join the hostedby with the datasource, and map only if datasource has pubsrepository::journal type
manifestations.biblio.start_page	journal.sp		
manifestations.biblio.end_page	journal.ep		
manifestations.biblio.volume	journal.volume		
manifestations.biblio.edition	journal.edition		
manifestations.biblio.number	journal.number		
manifestations.biblio.publisher	publisher.name		
manifestations.biblio.series			
manifestations.venue	concat(venue_____,md5(instance.hostedby.key))		This can be confusing since OpenAIRE does not have

			identifiers for Venues yet.
manifestations.hosting_datasource	instance.hostedby.key		
relevant_organizations	list of organization in the affiliation relationship with the result as a list of organization.local_identifier		
funding	list of projects in a relation with outcome with the result as a list [grant.local_identifier]		
related_products.relation_type	list of results.local_identifier which are in relation with this result considering one of the mappable relations	mapped relations: cites isSupplementedBy isDocumentedBy isNewVersionOf isPartOf	
related_products.products	list of products related to each relation type as list of product.local_identifier		

Organization

SKG-IF PROPERTY	OPENAIRE PROPERTY	NOTES	COMMENTS
local_identifier	id		
identifiers.schema	pid.qualifier.schemeid	list	
identifiers.value	pid.value		
name	legalname.value		
short_name	legalshortname.value		
other_names	alternative_names.value	list	
website	websiteurl.value		
country	country.classid		
type		map relevant types from the ec* fields of organisations. If no match, default to "other"	

Venue

SKG-IF PROPERTY	OPENAIRE PROPERTY	NOTES	COMMENTS
local_identifier	concat(venue ::,md5(datasource.id))	the datasource must not have the	concatenating venue to the datasource id to create a new identifier specific for venue entities

		type aggregator	otherwise both datasource and venue would have the same local identifier
identifiers.scheme	issn, lissn, eissn	it is a list, so it will have one entry for any of the issn not null in the result	
identifiers.value	datasource.journal.issnPrinted, datasource.journal.lissn, datasource.journal.eissn		
identifiers.scheme	pid.dataInfo.qualifier.classid		
identifiers.value	pid.value		
acronym			
type	if one of the issns exists for the datasource => journal if datasource.type.classid = datarepository::unknown or pubsrepository::institutional or pubsrepository::unknown pr orprepository or softwarerepository or pubsrepository::thematic => repository else unknown		
is_currently_full_oa	not mappable		
creation_date	not mappable		
contributions.person	not mappable		
contributions.roles	not mappable		

Data sources

SKG-IF PROPERTY	OPENAIRE PROPERTY	NOT ES	COMMENTS
local_identifier	id		
identifiers.schema	pid.qualifier.classid	list	
identifiers.value	pid.value		
name	officialname.value		
submission_policy_url	submissionpolicyurl		
preservation_policy_url	preservationpolicyurl		
version_control	versioncontrol	bool	

persistent_identity_systems.product_type	researchentitytype	list	type to be remapped to the eosk types
persistent_identity_systems.pid_scheme	pidsystems.value		when not null. It can be a string with multiple values
jurisdiction	jurisdiction.calssid		
data_source_classification	eoscdatasourcetype.classname		
research_product_type	researchentitytype	list	type to be remapped to the eosk types
thematic	thematic	bool	
research_product_license.name	not mappable	list	
research_product_license.url	not mappable		
research_product_access_policy	databaseaccesstype if open => open access (https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/access_rights/c_abf2/) if restricted => restricted access (https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/access_rights/c_16ec/) if closed => metadata only access (https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/access_rights/c_14cb/)	list	
research_product_metadata_license.name	not mappable	list	
research_product_metadata_license.url	not mappable		
research_product_metadata_access_policy	researchproductmetadataspolicies	list	with the same mapping of research_product_access_policy

Grant

SKG-IF PROPERTY	OPENAIRE PROPERTY	NOTES	COMMENTS
local_identifier	id		
identifiers.schema	pid.qualifier.classid		
identifiers.value	pid.value		

identifiers.schema	funder acronym	to be used the xpath //fundingtree/funder/shortname	
identifiers.value	project.code		
title	title.value		
abstract	summary.value		
acronym	acronym.value		
funder	fundingtree	to be used the xpath //funder/name	
funding_stream	fundingtree	to be used the xpath //funding_level_[n]	
currency	currency.value		
funded_amount	fundedamount.value		
keywords	subject.value		
start_date	startdate.value		
end_date	enddate.value		
website	websiteurl.value		
beneficiaries	organization.id	for the organizations in the relation with semantic class isParticipant	produces the list of organization internal identifiers
contributors.person		I would not map it because we have only information regarding the person (if any) associated to the leading organization	
contributors.organization			
contributor.srole			

Person

SKG-IF PROPERTY	OPENAIRE PROPERTY	NOTES	COMMENTS
local_identifier	if author has orcid -> md5(concat(author.pid.value,Boolean.TRUE)); if author has orcid_pending -> md5(concat(author.pid.value,Boolean.FALSE)); if author does not have orcid -> md5(concat(result.id , author position in the author list))	derived from the data if no orcid/orcid pending is given or depending on orcid	
identifiers.scheme	result.author.pid.classid		
identifiers.value	result.author.pid.value		
given_name	result.author.name		
family_name	result.author.surname		

agent	result.author,fullname		
affiliations.organization		list	As it is now this information is not mappable from the graph
affiliations.start_date			
affiliations.end_date			

Topic

SKG-IF PROPERTY	OPENAIRE PROPERTY	NOT ES	COMMENTS
local_identifier	concat("topic_____:",md5(concat(result.subject.qualifier.classid,result.subject.value)))		
identifiers.scheme	result.subject.qualifier.classid		
identifiers.value	result.subject.value		
name	result.subject.value		